

Molecular Docking Studies, Synthesis, And Characterization of the Novel Benzothiazole Derivative as Beta Tryptase-II Inhibitor, A New Treatment Strategy for the Patient with Severe Asthma

Rima Mahapatra¹, Chiranjit Mandal², Lopamudra Chakravorty³, Sweta Das⁴

^{1,2}Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Calcutta Institute of Pharmaceutical Technology and AHS, Uluberia, Howrah-711316

³Department of Pharmacology, Calcutta Institute of Pharmaceutical Technology and AHS, Uluberia, Howrah-711316

⁴Department of Pharmaceutics, Calcutta Institute of Pharmaceutical Technology and AHS, Uluberia, Howrah-711316.

ABSTRACT

Beta tryptase, a serine protease produced from mast cells and a promising therapeutic target in severe and treatment-refractory asthma, is significantly associated with airway inflammation, mucus hypersecretion, and airway remodeling. In this work, we describe the synthesis and thorough characterization of a new benzothiazole derivative as a possible beta-tryptase-II inhibitor, following the design and molecular docking (PDB ID 2FS9) evaluation. Strong binding affinity and consistent interaction patterns between the benzothiazole scaffold and the Beta Tryptase-II active-site residues were observed in structure-based docking studies, indicating promising inhibitory potential. The structure of the compound was verified by ATR and NMR analyses after it was synthesized using a traditional heterocyclic condensation pathway. Acceptable drug-likeness and safety characteristics were also shown by in-silico ADME profiling. These results present a promising lead chemical based on benzothiazole that could aid in the creation of upcoming treatments that target Beta Tryptase-II, perhaps providing a fresh approach to treating patients with severe asthma.

Keywords: Benzothiazole, β -Tryptase, Inhibitors, Asthma, Remodeling, Synthesis, Characterization, Molecular docking.

INTRODUCTION

Airway inflammation, which causes the airways to narrow, swell, and frequently fill with excess mucus, is a symptom of asthma. Breathing problems, coughing, a whistling sound when exhaling, shortness of breath, and variable airflow obstruction with acute exacerbations can result from this. Many patients continue to suffer from uncontrollable symptoms and exacerbations caused by mechanisms unrelated to type 2 inflammation, even in the face of the development of additional biologic therapies that target this inflammation. [1-3] Asthma pathogenesis is significantly influenced by mast cells, which are

activated by releasing several pro-inflammatory mediators from cytosolic granules. Tryptase, the most prevalent granular protease, can cause hyperresponsiveness in the bronchi and encourage neutrophil and eosinophil infiltration into inflammatory tissues. Patients with severe asthma have higher tryptase levels in bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) fluid and sputum. Reducing serum tryptase levels by stopping mast cell development or activation can help lessen bronchial hyperreactivity in asthma patients. [1] Tryptase is a tetrameric enzyme that is part of the protease family called trypsin. It consists of four catalytic subunits that create a ring-like formation encircling an oval-shaped central opening. For its

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

biological purpose, this particular structure is essential. Tryptase's role in inflammatory reactions and allergies has been thoroughly investigated as a possible therapeutic target for several inflammatory diseases. Despite tryptase's critical role in biological processes such as fibrosis, angiogenesis, and immune response modulation, finding potent inhibitors has been challenging, mostly due to the complex mechanisms controlling its activation and regulation. The structure and function of tryptase must be understood in order to overcome this obstacle, as well as to develop creative methods to prevent its activities.^[4-6] C₇H₅NS is the chemical formula for benzothiazole, an aromatic heterocyclic molecule. It is found in many natural products and is a white, rather viscous liquid. Numerous medicinal compounds have been created and assessed using the

benzothiazole nucleus. We have recently investigated various novel synthesized benzothiazole and its condensed derivatives. 2-substituted benzothiazole exhibits broad biological and pharmacological activities, including anti-TB, anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, anticonvulsant activities, anthelmintic, neuroprotective, anti-malarial, and anti-tumour or cancer.^[7-13] In this work, we have performed the docking studies using PDB ID 2FS9 as beta tryptase II with inhibitor CRA-28427, which shows a promising docking score, so we have designed the synthetic pathway and done the synthesis and characterization of the novel benzothiazole derivative as a beta tryptase-II inhibitor.

SCHEME:

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

DOCKING

Molecular docking has advanced drug discovery by enabling structure-based analysis of ligand-receptor interactions. Firstly, we retrieve the 3D structure of the receptor protein (PDB ID: 2FS9), Human beta tryptase II with inhibitor CRA-28427 from the RCSB PDB (<https://www.rcsb.org/structure/2FS9>) in .pdb format. The receptor protein was prepared and optimized by removing the ligand and water

molecules, and by adding hydrogen atoms and AM1 BBC charges using UCSF Chimera. Then ligands were prepared using Chemdraw Ultra 8.0, energy minimized using Chem3D Ultra 8.0, and saved in .pdb format using UCSF Chimera, adding steric hydrogens and Gasteiger charges. Molecular docking was performed by using AutoDock 4.2.6, and visualization was done by using PMV and Chimera, and Discovery Studio.

Fig 1: Docking of protein and ligand

Table-1: RMSD TABLE

Rank	Sub-Rank	Run	Binding Energy	Cluster RMSD	Reference RMSD	Grep Pattern
1	1	4	-8.03	0.00	101.42	RANKING
1	2	8	-7.91	0.31	101.42	RANKING
1	3	1	-7.59	0.88	101.10	RANKING
2	1	3	-7.86	0.00	106.84	RANKING
2	2	5	-7.57	1.46	106.82	RANKING
3	1	6	-7.65	0.00	105.62	RANKING
3	2	2	-7.65	0.34	105.75	RANKING
4	1	10	-6.81	0.00	103.37	RANKING
5	1	9	-6.78	0.00	104.14	RANKING
6	1	7	-6.41	0.00	102.07	RANKING

SYNTHESIS

Synthesis of 7-chloro-6-fluorobenzo[d]thiazol-2-amine(3): Substituted aniline(3-chloro-4-fluoro-aniline) is treated with potassium thiocyanate(KSCN) in presence of bromine(Br) and acetic acid(CH₃COOH) at 0-5°C then the compound 3(7-

chloro-6-fluorobenzo[d]thiazol-2-amine) is produced.

is

Fig 2: Bromination

Synthesis of 1-(7-chloro-6-fluorobenzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)hydrazine (4): Then compound 3 was taken in the presence of hydrazine(NH₂NH₂), H₂O, HCL, and Ethylene glycol and refluxed for 3 hours to get compound 4.

Synthesis of (Z)-1-(7-chloro-6-fluorobenzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)-2-(1-phenylethylidene) hydrazine (5): In the presence of acetophenone in

ethanol/ glacial acetic acid, the compound 4 gives the compound 5, after refluxing for 5 hrs.

Synthesis of (Z)-6-fluoro-N-phenyl-2-(2-(1-phenylethylidene) hydrazinyl) benzo[d] thiazol-7-amine (6): Refluxed 2 hours with aniline to synthesize compound 6 in the presence of DMF.

Fig 3: Reflux

CHARACTERIZATION:

Fig- 4: IR and NMR spectra

7-chloro-6-fluorobenzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (3): Percentage yield 85%; M.P. 180–182°C; TLC: Cyclohexane: Ethyl acetate (9:1); Rf value: 0.675; little yellowish crystalline powder .IR (ATR) (-Cl) 720 cm^{-1} , (-F) 1390 cm^{-1} , (-NH) 3297 cm^{-1} .

1-(7-chloro-6-fluorobenzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)hydrazine (4): Yield 75%; white crystalline powder; M.P 197-199°C; TLC – Acetone: Ethyl Acetate(1:1), Rf value- 0.712, IR (ATR) (-Cl) 720 cm^{-1} , (-F) 1339 cm^{-1} , (-NH) 3480 cm^{-1} , (-NH) 2926 cm^{-1} .

(Z)-1-(7-chloro-6-fluorobenzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)-2-(1-phenylethylidene) hydrazine (5): Yield 75%; light yellowish crystalline powder; M.P 235-237°C; TLC –

Ethyl Acetate: Methanol(1:1), Rf value- 0.425, IR (ATR) (-Cl) 720 cm^{-1} , (-F) 1339 cm^{-1} , (-NH) 3480 cm^{-1} , (-NH) 2926 cm^{-1} .

(Z)-6-fluoro-N-phenyl-2-(2-(1-phenylethylidene)hydrazinyl)benzo[d] thiazol-7-amine(6): Yield 59%; white crystalline powder; M.P 249-251°C; TLC – Ethyl Acetate: Methanol(4:6), Rf value- 0.651, IR (ATR) (-Cl) 720 cm^{-1} , (-F) 1339 cm^{-1} , (-NH) 3480 cm^{-1} , (-NH) 2926, cm^{-1} (-CH) 2846 cm^{-1} . NMR (Solvent DMSO) CH (7.65t, J -1.0), CH (7.3t, J -1.08), CH (7.01m, J -1.62), CH (6.46d, J -0.73), CH (6.62s, J -0.73), NH (4.0 s, J -1.0), CH₃ (0.9s, J -1.06),

RESULTS:

Table 2: Docking Results

PDB ID	Ligands	Lowest Binding Energy
2FS9	C4A	-7.34
	Compound-6	-8.03

DISCUSSION:

To explore its potential as a selective Beta Tryptase-II inhibitor, a novel benzothiazole-based drug was developed, produced, and evaluated using molecular docking. Beta tryptase, a serine protease produced from mast cells and a promising therapeutic target in severe and treatment-refractory asthma, is significantly associated with airway inflammation,

mucus hypersecretion, and airway remodeling. The compound's potential as a lead molecule for future anti-asthmatic drug development is supported by positive results from both computational and experimental analyses. The synthesis of the benzothiazole derivative was successfully achieved through a simple and reproducible method, confirming the feasibility of constructing this scaffold

for pharmaceutical applications. Spectroscopic analyses (ATR and NMR) verified the structural integrity of the synthesized compound, as all characteristic peaks and functional groups aligned with the expected chemical structure. Its potential for further biological testing is further supported by its chemical stability and purity.

CONCLUSION:

According to the study's findings, the newly developed benzothiazole derivative shows promise as a potential beta tryptase-II inhibitor for treating severe asthma. This compound could help create targeted therapies that address the underlying inflammatory processes rather than just alleviating symptoms, pending validation of its expected inhibitory activity through further biological research. The study's findings indicate that the recently created benzothiazole derivative exhibits potential as a beta tryptase-II inhibitor for the treatment of severe asthma.

REFERENCES

- Rhee et al. "Airway tryptase levels inform the lack of clinical efficacy of the tryptase inhibitor MTPS9579A in asthma" *Allergy*. 2024; 79: 2993–3004.
- William M. Abraham "Tryptase: potential role in airway inflammation and remodeling" *hysiol Lung Cell Mol Physiol* 2002;282: 193–196.
- Bachelet, Munitz & Levi-Schaffer "Tryptase as an inflammatory marker in allergic disease and asthma" *Expert Rev. Clin. Immunol.* 2005;1(1): 63–73
- Muhammad Yasir et al. "Identification of Potential Tryptase Inhibitors from FDA-Approved Drugs Using Machine Learning, Molecular Docking, and Experimental Validation" *ACS Omega* 2024; 9: 38820–38831
- J.A. Cairns. "Inhibitors of mast cell tryptase beta as therapeutics for the treatment of asthma and inflammatory disorders" *Pulmonary Pharmacology & Therapeutics* 2005; 18: 55–66
- Berlin, F. et al. "Andersson, C.K. Mast Cell Tryptase Promotes Airway Remodeling by Inducing Anti-Apoptotic and Cell Growth Properties in Human Alveolar and Bronchial Epithelial Cells." *Cells* 2023,12, 1439-1455
- Combrink et al. "1,2-Benzisothiazol-3-one 1,1-Dioxide Inhibitors of Human Mast Cell Tryptase" *J. Med. Chem.* 1998; 41: 4854-4860.
- Kyle C Elrod & Robert P Numerof. "Emerging therapeutic targets in asthma: the rationale for mast cell tryptase inhibition" *Emerg. Ther. Targets* 1999; 3(2): 203-212.
- E. M. Erin et al. "Effects of a reversible b-tryptase and trypsin inhibitor (RWJ-58643) on nasal allergic responses" *Clin. Exp. Allergy* 2006;36: 458–464.
- Sarah F. G et al. "A Novel, Nonpeptidic, Orally Active Bivalent Inhibitor of Human β -Tryptase" *Pharmacology* 2018;102:233–243
- Guay et al. "Targeting Serine Proteases in Asthma" *Curr Top Med Chem.*, 2006; 6: 393-402
- S. He, A. F. Walls. "Human mast cell tryptase: a stimulus of microvascular leakage and mast cell activation" *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* 1997; 328:89-97
- Krishna et al. "Inhibition of mast cell tryptase by inhaled APC 366 attenuates allergen-induced late-phase airway obstruction in asthma." *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 2001; 107: 1039-1045
- R.S. Lan et al. "Role of protease-activated receptors in airway function: a target for therapeutic intervention" *Pharmacol & Ther.* 2002; 95: 239 – 257
- S. Lee et al. "Design of novel, potent, and selective human b-tryptase inhibitors based on a-keto-[1,2,4]-oxadiazoles" *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* (2006);16: 4036–4040
- Y. Miyazaki et al. "Synthesis and evaluation of 4-substituted benzylamine derivatives as β -tryptase inhibitors" *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* 2006;16: 2986–2990
- R P Numerof, P J Simpson & RTanaka. "Tryptase inhibitors: a novel class of anti-inflammatory drugs" *Exp. Opin. Invest. Drugs* 1997; 6(7): 811-817
- C.P. Sommerhoffl and N. Schaschke. "Mast Cell Tryptase - as a Target in Allergic Inflammation: An Evolving Story" *Curr. Pharm. Des.* 2007; 13: 313-332
- W.S.F. Wong, K.P. Leong. "Tyrosine kinase inhibitors: a new approach for asthma" *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta* 1697 (2004) 53–69
- R.K. Lambert, B.R. Wiggs, K. Kuwano, J.C. Hogg, P.D. "Pare, Functional significance of

- increased airway smooth muscle in asthma and COPD” *J. Appl. Physiol.* 74 (1993) 2771 – 2781.
21. Rice KD, Gangloff AR, Kuo EY, Dener JM, Wang VR, Lum R, et al. “Dibasic inhibitors of human mast cell tryptase. Part 1: synthesis and optimization of a novel class of inhibitors.” *Bioorg Med Chem Lett* 2000; 10: 2357-60.
22. Molinari JF, Scuri M, Moore WR et al. “Inhaled tryptase causes bronchoconstriction in sheep via histamine release.” *Am. J. Resp. Crit. Care Med.* 1996; 154: 649-653.
23. Bingham, C. O. 3rd, & Austen, K. F. “Mast-cell responses in the development of asthma.” *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 2002; 105: 527 – 534.
24. Zhao G, Bolton SA, Kwon C, Hartl KS, Seiler SM, Slusarchyk WA, et al. Synthesis of potent and selective 2-azepanone inhibitors of human tryptase. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett* 2004; 14: 309-12.
25. García M, et al. “Design, synthesis, and biological activity of a targeted library of potential tryptase inhibitors.” *Org Biomol Chem* 2004; 2: 1633-42.

HOW TO CITE: Rima Mahapatra, Chiranjit Mandal, Lopamudra Chakravorty, Sweta Das, Molecular Docking Studies, Synthesis, And Characterization of the Novel Benzothiazole Derivative as Beta Tryptase-II Inhibitor, A New Treatment Strategy for the Patient with Severe Asthma, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (3), 167-173. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18929801>

